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Am I interrupting or supporting? Associations between teachers' roles in free play and children's playfulness

Cornelia Rüdüsüli^a, Isabelle Duss^b, Patricia Lannen^{b†}, and Corina Wustmann Seiler^{a†}

^aDepartment of Research and Development, Zurich University of Teacher Education, Zurich, Switzerland; ^bMarie Meierhofer Children's Institute, University of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

ABSTRACT

Free play is recognized in early childhood education and care (ECEC) as a crucial form of learning, and children's disposition to engage in play is termed playfulness. The emphasis that free play places on children's autonomy and self-control raises questions about teachers' roles in this learning environment to encourage children's engagement in play. This study explores the cross-sectional and longitudinal relationships between the roles that teachers ($n = 62$) adopt during free play and the playfulness of children in ECEC ($n = 393$; $M_{\text{age}} = 4.5$ years; $SD_{\text{age}} = 1.3$). Teachers' roles were assessed through standardized live observations, and children's playfulness was assessed with a questionnaire completed by parents and teachers, once at the same time as the observations and again 1 year later. Cross-sectionally, no significant associations were found. However, longitudinal results showed a small positive association between the onlooker role and children's playfulness, demonstrating the importance of both teachers' presence and children's autonomy in free play. Further moderation analysis revealed that the impact of teachers' roles on children's playfulness at T2 depended on children's initial levels of playfulness. These findings demonstrate the importance of tailoring practice sensitively to the children's stage of development.

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Introduction

Free play is fundamental to young children's learning and development in Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC; Pyle et al., 2017). However, free play is a challenging learning setting for teachers, as they must balance fostering children's autonomy with their pedagogical responsibility to support children's development (Jensen et al., 2019). Despite its importance, research on how teachers' behavior during free play influences children's engagement and playfulness is limited (Skene et al., 2022). The present study explores the relationship between teachers' roles during children's play and children's playfulness, a construct that captures the essence of playful behavior across various situations. The cross-sectional and longitudinal findings aim to guide teachers in ensuring high-quality play experiences that support playful learning and development.

CONTACT Corina Wustmann Seiler Department of Research and Development, Zurich University of Teacher Education, Lagerstrasse 2, Zürich 8090, Switzerland

[†]These authors share senior last authorship.

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Playful pedagogy in early childhood education and care

In ECEC, free play is regarded as a key learning setting because it provides children with intrinsically motivated experiences essential to their overall development and as a foundation for later learning success (Whitebread et al., 2017). In this setting, children have the freedom to direct their play, choose activities that align with their interests, and control the flow of their activities (Wood, 2014). However, free play is both a child-directed activity and an educational setting, and thus the significance of teachers' roles during children's play remains unclear. Playful pedagogy supports children in learning meaningfully and actively and fostering positive emotions and social interactions (Zosh et al., 2018). In a child-directed environment, children are free to explore without fear of making mistakes, which strengthens their self-confidence and encourages them to expand their skills across various domains (McInnes et al., 2011). The potential for learning through play is maximized when children are fully engaged and immersed in their play experiences (Cornelli Sanderson, 2010).

Children's playfulness

A child's approach to play, known as playfulness, is a capacity of the child that develops through interaction with their environment (Cornelli Sanderson, 2010). Playfulness is understood as children's enjoyment and motivation to engage in play (Barnett, 1991). Playful children are described as spontaneous, active, joyful, and flexible, which are crucial characteristics when dealing with new challenges and form the foundation for lifelong learning (Skard & Bundy, 2008). Furthermore, studies have linked playfulness to adaptive coping skills, emotion regulation, and creativity (e.g., Ata & Macun, 2022).

Children's playfulness can be assessed through questionnaires completed by the children's caregivers (e.g., Children's Playfulness Scale, Barnett, 1991) and through observation (e.g., Test of Playfulness, Skard & Bundy, 2008). Questionnaire-based assessments are situation-independent and enable the consideration of diverse perspectives such as those of parents and teachers. Conversely, observational assessments provide an evaluation by an external objective rater in specific play situations. For example, research has shown that children exhibit varying levels of playfulness across different play contexts: One study found that typically developing children were more playful in interactions with their mothers than with their teachers (Pinchover et al., 2016). Although manifestations of children's playfulness may vary across situations, playfulness is commonly conceptualized as a relatively stable situation-independent capacity for play. This view is supported by empirical findings indicating that the dimensions of playfulness assessed through observational measures correlate with those captured through questionnaire-based instruments. This suggests that both approaches reflect similar underlying aspects of children's playfulness (Bundy et al., 2001; Muys et al., 2006).

Encouraging children's playfulness in ECEC

There is ongoing debate in research and practice about how teachers should support children's free play. Providing appropriate play support tailored to children's needs can enhance the complexity of their play with potentially positive effects on their socio-

emotional and cognitive development (e.g., Perren et al., 2019; Vu et al., 2015). In contrast, children may perceive the excessive involvement of the teacher as intrusive, potentially decreasing their engagement and play complexity (Frost et al., 2005; Gmitrova & Gmitrov, 2003). However, whether children’s engagement in play consistently increases after experiencing more complex play facilitated by teacher support remains uncertain. Additionally, teachers may inadvertently impose a specific play style that enhances complexity but conflicts with children’s interests and cultural play experiences (Brown & Freeman, 2001).

Research exploring playfulness within family contexts reveals the significance of the quality of parent–child relationships, parental play supportiveness, responsiveness, and sensitivity (Fung & Chung, 2022; Wustmann Seiler et al., 2024). In an institutional context, Driscoll and Pianta (2010) suggest that teachers’ involvement in children’s play can foster a positive teacher–child relationship. However, teachers’ engagement in children’s play tends to be more rigid and less playful. This rigidity arises because teachers are influenced by curriculum requirements and parental expectations and thus frequently prioritize goal-directed activities during free play (Canaslan-Akyar & Sevimli-Celik, 2021; Gmitrova & Gmitrov, 2003). The impact of such goal-directed activities on children’s playfulness is evident in Rüdüsüli et al.’s (2024) findings, which indicate a slightly negative longitudinal relationship between teachers’ high-quality learning support, such as language modeling and feedback quality, and children’s later playfulness. In contrast to parents, teachers pursue pedagogical aims with specific objectives that may be challenging to integrate into child-directed play. Vartiainen et al. (2024) refer to the paradox of play-based learning, in which institutional frameworks mandate external goals such as promoting children’s cognition and language rather than valuing the play as an end in itself. Hence, to better understand teachers’ specific roles during children’s free play, it is crucial to differentiate varieties of teachers’ behavior in interactions with children in play-based learning activities.

Teachers’ roles during free play

Numerous researchers have investigated teachers’ behavior during children’s free play and used various methodological qualitative and quantitative approaches, such as observations and questionnaires (e.g., Ivrendi, 2020; Johnson et al., 2005; Wustmann Seiler et al., 2022), to identify a range of roles that teachers assume. Building on Ivrendi’s (2020) work, Rüdüsüli et al. (2023) developed a conceptual framework that classifies the seven most prominent roles in teachers’ behavior during free play in external observations: co-player, director, tutor and stage manager, redirector, classroom manager, onlooker, and uninvolved. The conceptual framework categorizes teachers’

Table 1. Conceptual framework of teachers’ roles during children’s free play (Rüdüsüli et al., 2023).

Reference to children’s play	Activity level	Active			Passive
		Proactive		Reactive	
With reference	Co-Player	Director	Tutor & Stage Manager		Onlooker
Without reference	Redirector	Classroom Manager		Uninvolved	

roles during children's free play by two criteria: the extent to which teachers' behavior relates to the children's ongoing play activity and the level of the teachers' active involvement in the play (see [Table 1](#)). The relation to the children's play is determined by whether the teacher's actions and statements are directly connected to the children's current play, such as building a structure or engaging in pretend play. Simply acknowledging the play's content is insufficient to demonstrate a genuine connection to the children's play activity. For example, if children are playing with animal figures and constructing a zoo with wooden blocks, and the teacher, acting as a redirector, asks if they have ever been to a zoo, this does not fully engage with the children's play. In contrast, if the teacher, in the role of director, says something like "watch out, the fence is broken, and the animal has escaped from the zoo," this would be a clear reference to the children's play activity. Active role behavior of the teacher is differentiated according to whether the teacher proactively takes the initiative or reacts to the children's immediate needs as they play; these active roles are described in detail in [Rüdisüli et al. \(2023\)](#). In passive roles, teachers do not actively interact with the children during play. In the role of onlooker, the teachers act as an attentive audience for the children's play activities. They withdraw from the play and consciously observe the children's play processes. They show presence and give brief non-verbal and verbal signals of recognition and appreciation while observing. In the uninvolved role, teachers focus on other tasks unrelated to the children's ongoing play. For example, they are busy tidying up, talking to other adults on the phone, or doing administrative work.

The conceptual framework combines the roles of tutor and stage manager, as both share the same level of activity and reference to children's play. Although they differ, with the tutor being focused on the activity itself and the stage manager on the play environment, they were operationalized and assessed as one single role by [Rüdisüli et al. \(2023\)](#). Similarly, although the co-player and director roles were categorized equally in both dimensions of activity level and play reference, they were kept as separate roles to account for the teachers' positioning as either co-player within the play or director outside the children's play ([Rüdisüli et al., 2023](#)). The distinction between positioning in the proactive roles is important because children are more likely to accept teacher-initiated interactions if the teacher positions themselves within the play and interacts in a playful way as a co-player ([Gaviria-Loaiza et al., 2017](#)). However, the conceptual framework does not reflect any quality rating of the roles and simply categorizes the teachers' behavior without evaluating it. It is difficult to compare findings about teachers' role preferences of previous research due to the heterogeneity of methods of data collection, ECEC settings, children's ages, and the definition of roles. For example, the way the director role was assessed in [Rüdisüli et al.'s \(2023\)](#) study reflects a broader view of proactive support for children's play than the control and guidance originally defined by [Johnson et al. \(2005\)](#). Although teachers change their roles depending on the situation, evidence is emerging that teachers have role preferences that are predicted more by teachers' characteristics, such as their work experience and professional self-efficacy, and less by the type of play children are engaged in ([Rüdisüli et al., 2023](#); [Wustmann Seiler et al., 2022](#)). The more teachers perceived themselves as self-effective, the more they were observed in the role of redirectors, who refocus children's attention to formal learning without reference to their play ([Rüdisüli et al., 2023](#)). This result underscores the perceived pressure on teachers to direct children's play toward developing specific academic-oriented skills ([Vartiainen et al., 2024](#)). Further predictors

at the teacher and classroom level have been examined in several questionnaire-based studies, showing a heterogeneous pattern of findings that may be explained by differences in cultural contexts and ECEC settings (Grigoropoulos, 2023; Ivrendi, 2020; Wustmann Seiler et al., 2022).

Significance of teachers' roles during free play

Findings from sociodramatic play research indicate that teachers contribute to the complexity of children's play by assuming roles like stage manager, co-player, and tutor (Perren et al., 2019; Vu et al., 2015). In contrast, when teachers remain uninvolved, children's play tends to be less complex. Moreover, when teachers assume the roles of director or redirector and dominate the play, it often results in a loss of spontaneity and complexity in the children's play (Enz & Christie, 1993). To the best of our knowledge, the relationships and effects of teachers' roles on children's playfulness have not yet been investigated independently of the play situation. Johnson et al. (2005) conceptualized teachers' roles in children's play in an additional conceptual framework along a continuum, ranging from no involvement to complete dominance. At the extreme ends of this continuum (e.g., uninvolved and redirector), the roles are described as impeding, because both insufficient and excessive involvement can negatively impact children's play. In contrast, roles positioned in the center (e.g., onlooker, stage manager, and co-player) are seen as facilitative, because teachers' appropriate involvement may enrich children's play. This categorization is grounded in case studies (Enz & Christie, 1993) and has since been widely referenced in the literature (e.g., Gaviria-Loaiza et al., 2017; Ivrendi, 2020). Beyond conceptual classification, Johnson et al. (2005) concluded that providing effective play support is a complex pedagogical challenge that requires teachers to find a balance between being responsive and avoiding intrusiveness. The importance of developmentally appropriate practice has also been highlighted by authors stressing that teachers should respond to children's needs when fostering play (Johnson et al., 2005; Trawick-Smith & Dziurgot, 2011). Studies in the familial context showed that parents are more involved in children's play when the children are younger or less cognitively developed (Duss et al., 2024; Warash et al., 2017).

Summary and present study

Free play is essential for learning in ECEC, but there is limited research on the effect of teachers' roles on children's play and development. Teachers adopt various roles during free play, ideally adjusting their support to the children's needs. Traditionally, these roles are classified as impeding or facilitative. However, this classification is based on children's reactions to teachers' behavior in specific situations and on the complexity of children's play (e.g., Enz & Christie, 1993). Focusing on children's playfulness can offer a broader perspective on children's play engagement independently of specific situations. The interplay between children's playfulness and teachers' roles remains underexplored, but understanding this connection is crucial to the professional development of ECEC teachers to better support playful learning.

The present study examines cross-sectional and longitudinal relations between various teachers' roles in children's free play, assessed by standardized external observations, and children's playfulness. Children's playfulness was measured with questionnaires completed

by teachers and parents in a multi-informant approach to consider both institutional and familial perspectives. Additionally, the study examined whether the associations between teachers' roles and children's playfulness over time differed depending on children's initial level of playfulness. The following research questions were addressed:

- (1) Which roles that teachers assume during children's free play affect children's playfulness cross-sectionally and longitudinally?
- (2) Does the initial level of children's playfulness moderate the longitudinal associations between teachers' roles during children's free play and children's playfulness 1 year later?

The relations between teachers' roles and children's playfulness were investigated exploratorily, without formulating hypotheses, due to the limited state of research.

Method

Procedure

The present study forms part of a project named "Playfulness in early childhood: A longitudinal study of individual and contextual determinants (Playful)." The Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Philosophy at the University of Zurich, Switzerland, reviewed and approved the study (ethics approval number 20.12.13). Participants were recruited through an open call directed at Switzerland's ECEC institutions: childcare centers and kindergartens. Childcare centers are private institutions for children from infancy onward, and kindergartens, which are obligatory for children aged four and typically last for 2 years, are part of the public school system. Kindergarten teachers usually hold bachelor's degrees, whereas those in childcare centers have completed vocational training. Despite differences in funding, age range, and staff qualifications, both childcare centers and kindergartens prioritize free play as a fundamental aspect of early education. In both settings, children spend a substantial part of their day engaged in free play, during which they can move freely and choose among various play areas and activities within the classroom environment. In Switzerland, as in many Western countries, play is defined as a child-directed activity involving minimal adult involvement (Weisberg et al., 2013). Teachers are therefore expected to grant children a high degree of autonomy. At the same time, play is recognized as a valuable context for learning, emphasizing teachers' participation as an opportunity to purposefully enrich children's learning experiences (Zosh et al., 2018).

For study participation, teachers and parents provided written consent. Teachers were informed that the researchers would conduct classroom observations lasting about 4 hours, either in the morning or in the afternoon. The observations focused on aspects of pedagogical practice and the play and learning environment, with the request to provide ample opportunity for children's free play during the observation. During the initial assessment (T1) in spring 2021, we assessed teachers' roles during free play in ECEC with standardized observations. Concurrently, an online questionnaire was used to assess children's playfulness as reported by parents and teachers. A year later (T2), parents and teachers provided ratings for children's playfulness with the same questionnaire. The questionnaires were

conducted online with Survalyzer software. The analysis focused on those children that remained with the same teacher throughout both measurements.

Participants

At the initial assessment (T1), the sample included 62 early childhood education and care (ECEC) teachers, comprising 25 teachers from childcare centers and 37 from kindergartens. The participants' ages ranged between 23 and 63 years, with an average age of 38.2 years ($SD = 11.7$). Their professional experience varied from 1 to 37 years, averaging 13.8 years ($SD = 9.9$). The majority of participants (95.1%) were female, and 90.2% identified as having Swiss origins.

Altogether, 393 children aged 2 to 6 years ($M_{age} = 4.5$; $SD_{age} = 1.3$) participated in the study at both assessment points. The majority of children (82.8%) were of Swiss origin, and 88.5% primarily spoke German at home. Among them, 44.8% attended childcare centers, while 55.2% were enrolled in kindergarten. Additionally, nearly half of the children's mothers (49.8%) had a university degree, and 41.3% had completed vocational training. The groups in ECEC settings varied in size, ranging from 2 to 15 children per group ($M = 6.3$, $SD = 2.8$). In total, 44.8% were enrolled in childcare centers, and 55.2% attended kindergarten.

Measures

Teachers' roles during free play

Teachers' roles during free play were assessed in a standardized observation with the Teacher Roles during Free play – Observation scale (Rüdisüli et al., 2023), which is based on the conceptual framework described above. In total, seven roles were observed, categorized into three proactive roles, co-player, director, and redirector, two reactive roles, tutor and stage manager and classroom manager, and two passive roles, onlooker and uninvolved. Five trained researchers observed teachers' behavior during sequences of children's free play, excluding routine or teacher-guided activities, in observation cycles of 15–20 minutes, aiming to capture the typical experience of a half-day in ECEC. Depending on how much time was allocated to free play during the half-day, three to five observation cycles were conducted. After each observation cycle, the observers rated the occurrence of the teacher's roles on a five-point scale (1 = never, 2 = rarely, 3 = sometimes, 4 = often, 5 = always). To ensure quality control, 19% of the observation cycles were assessed by a second rater, resulting in satisfactory interrater reliability for the teachers' roles ($ICC = .72-.93$). The researchers were trained in a 1-day session with videos.

Children's playfulness

At both measurement points, children's playfulness was evaluated using the German adaptation of the Children's Playfulness Scale (Barnett, 1991; Wustmann Seiler et al., 2021). This scale measures children's playfulness across five dimensions: (1) manifest joy, (2) cognitive spontaneity, (3) social spontaneity, (4) sense of humor, and (5) physical spontaneity. It includes 23 items, each rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (doesn't sound at all like the child) to 5 (sounds exactly like the child). An exploratory factor analysis was conducted to explore the underlying factorial structure. Subsequently,

four items were excluded due to low factor loadings or item loadings on more than one factor (the items with the descriptive parameters are listed in [Appendix](#)). However, all five dimensions were empirically replicated. The manifest total score of children's playfulness was derived as the mean of these five dimensions. Internal consistency (Cronbach's Alpha $\alpha_{T1} = 0.67$; $\alpha_{T2} = 0.79$) and test-retest reliability ($r = 0.81$ ($p < .001$)) for the total playfulness scores were acceptable. To obtain a broad assessment of children's playfulness, we used reports from both parents and teachers, because play behavior can vary across various environments and playmates. The Pearson correlations between parent and teacher ratings indicated a positive association at T1 ($r = .46$, $p < .001$) and at T2 ($r = .36$, $p < .001$), suggesting a reasonable level of agreement while still capturing context-specific differences. By averaging both sets of responses, we sought to capture a more accurate representation of each child's playfulness and reduce potential biases from observing the child solely in one context (Rentzou, 2013).

Data analysis

Initially, descriptive statistics and bivariate correlations were computed for all variables included in the study. Subsequently, a regression analysis was conducted to investigate the cross-sectional and longitudinal associations of teachers' roles and children's playfulness during free play. Due to the low correlation between the roles, all roles were included in the model simultaneously. To reduce the complexity of the model, children's playfulness was included as a manifest dependent variable calculated as a mean of all five dimensions. Due to its predictive significance in previous studies, children's age was added as a control variable (e.g., Wustmann Seiler et al., 2024). In the longitudinal analysis, the same structure was applied; however, children's playfulness at T1 was also entered as a second control variable. All predictors were permitted to correlate with each other. Finally, we examined the interaction effect of children's initial playfulness at T1 and teachers' roles during free play on children's playfulness at T2 in seven moderation analyses separately for each role and controlled for children's age and children's playfulness at T1. We analyzed the results with Bonferroni's correction ($p = .005$) to account for alpha error accumulation.

The model fit for the regression model was satisfactory [$\chi^2(7) = 9.74$, $p = .20$, CFI = 0.992, RMSEA = 0.032, SRMR = 0.048], and the moderation models were all saturated. We used the Huber-White sandwich estimator (Freedman, 2006) to account for the hierarchical structure of the data, where children were nested within ECEC groups (ICC Playfulness T1 = 0.148; ICC Playfulness T2 = 0.107). To handle missing data, we employed the full information maximum likelihood method. All analyses were conducted using Mplus version 8.8 (Muthén & Muthén, 2017).

Descriptive statistics and intercorrelations

Table 2 presents mean scores and bivariate correlations of all study variables. Both measurements of children's playfulness correlated significantly and positively with each other. Comparing the frequency of teachers' roles in free play, the reactive roles (tutor and stage manager, classroom manager) were observed most frequently, followed by the passive roles (onlooker, uninvolved) and then the proactive roles (co-player, director, redirector). Several roles were significantly intercorrelated. The passive roles were mainly negatively correlated

Table 2. Descriptive statistics and bivariate correlations of all study variables.

	N	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Children's playfulness scores													
1	393	3.91	0.40	1									
2	393	4.0	0.47	.810***	1								
Teachers' roles during free play													
3	393	1.68	0.55	.050	.016	1							
4	393	1.83	0.75	.030	.031	-.036	1						
5	393	1.80	0.74	.048	.099*	-.072	-.022	1					
6	393	2.63	0.79	-.042	-.132**	.122*	-.089	-.358***	1				
7	393	2.22	0.66	.010	-.034	-.114*	-.057	.043	-.045	1			
8	393	1.94	0.82	.082	.133**	.052	-.213***	-.071	-.233***	.135**	1		
9	393	1.85	0.73	-.044	.004	-.111*	-.202***	-.272***	-.223***	-.207***	.005	1	
Control variable													
10	393	54.22	15.31	.218***	.203***	-.110*	.210***	.106*	-.090	-.010	-.006	-.241***	1

Note: * $p < .050$; ** $p < .010$; *** $p < .001$.
^ain months.

with the active roles at a low level. The highest negative correlation was found between the proactive role of redirector and the reactive role of tutor and stage manager. Bivariate correlations between teachers' roles and the total scores of children's playfulness indicated no significant correlation for T1. The playfulness score at T2 exhibited a low significant negative correlation with the role of tutor and stage manager and a low significant positive correlation with the roles of redirector and onlooker. No other roles were significantly correlated with the playfulness scores. Children's age was significantly positively correlated to both playfulness measurements. In addition, a low but significant positive correlation was found between children's age and the roles of director and redirector, and a negative correlation occurred between children's age and the roles of co-player and uninvolved.

Associations between teachers' roles during free play and children's playfulness

Standardized results of the regression model for the associations between teachers' roles and children's playfulness at both measurements are reported in Table 3. None of the roles significantly predicted the total score of children's playfulness cross-sectionally at T1. Only age was significantly positively related to children's playfulness at T1 at a low level. Longitudinally, children's age was no longer evident. However, as Table 3 indicates, the onlooker role had a small significant and positive association with the playfulness score at T2. In addition, there were two small but marginally significant associations with the playfulness score at T2: The role of redirector was positively related to children's playfulness, and the classroom manager negatively so. No other roles had significant associations with children's playfulness at T2. However, all the associations with teachers' roles were small, and the variance is mainly explained by the initial level of children's playfulness at T1.

The moderating effect of the initial level of children's playfulness

Two interaction effects for the redirector and the uninvolved role were found to be small and significant, but each with a different direction (see Table 4). For the redirector role, the interaction effect was negative. This means, as illustrated in Figure 1, that if children had higher initial levels of playfulness at T1 and teachers

Table 3. Standardized regression coefficients of the regression model.

	Playfulness T1 β (SE)	Playfulness T2 β (SE)
Age ^a	.23 (0.07)***	.02 (0.04)
Playfulness T1	–	.80 (0.02)***
Co-Player	.08 (0.07)	–.02 (0.03)
Director	.02 (0.06)	.02 (0.04)
Redirector	.06 (0.08)	.06 (0.03) [†]
Tutor & Stage Manager	.03 (0.08)	–.05 (0.04)
Classroom Manager	.02 (0.06)	–.05 (0.03) [†]
Onlooker	.09 (0.07)	.07 (0.03)*
Uninvolved	.05 (0.10)	.04 (0.04)
R ²	.07 (0.02)*	.68 (0.03)***

^ain months; β = Standardized regression coefficients, SE = standard errors, R² = coefficient of determination.

[†] $p < .100$; * $p < .050$; ** $p < .010$; *** $p < .001$.

Table 4. Unstandardized coefficients of the seven separate moderation models predicting children's playfulness at T2.

		Children's playfulness T2 b (SE)						
Moderation with the teachers' roles		Co-Player	Director	Redirector	Tutor & stage manager	Classroom manager	Onlooker	Uninvolved
Intercept	playfulness T2	3.95 (0.46)***	3.86 (0.09)***	4.11 (0.08)***	4.76 (0.52)***	3.76 (0.54)***	3.77 (0.42)***	2.92 (0.29)***
Teachers' role		-.03 (0.27)	.01 (0.021)	.02 (0.02)	.24 (0.20)	-.12 (0.24)	-.05 (0.21)	-.52 (0.15)
Playfulness T1		.75 (0.13)***	.93 (0.05)***	.98 (0.05)***	1.14 (0.13)***	.90 (0.14)***	.90 (0.13)***	.67 (0.10)***
Age ^a		.00 (0.00)	.00 (0.00)	.00 (0.00)	.00 (0.001)	.00 (0.00)	.00 (0.00)	.00 (0.00)
Playfulness T1 × teachers' role		.00 (0.07)	.01 (0.01)	-.01 (0.00)*	-.08(0.05)	.02 (0.06)	.02 (0.05)	.14 (0.04)***
R ²		.66 (0.03)***	0.661***	0.668***	0.669***	0.659***	0.662***	0.669***
ΔR ²		0.00	0.004	0.007	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.009

^ain months; b = Unstandardized regression coefficients; SE = standard errors; R² = coefficient of determination; ΔR² Difference to the model without interaction. significance criterion according to Bonferroni: †p < .01; *p < .005; **p < .001; ***p = .000.

Figure 1. Interaction playfulness T1 × redirector role.

Figure 2. Interaction playfulness T1 × uninvolved role.

were observed more frequently to adopt the role of redirector, children’s playfulness was lower at T2. In contrast, the interaction effect was positive for the uninvolved role. If children had higher initial levels of playfulness at T1 and teachers were observed more frequently to adopt the uninvolved role, children’s playfulness was higher at T2 (see [Figure 2](#)). However, less than 1% of the variance was explained by these interactions.

Discussion

This study aimed to investigate whether teachers’ roles during children’s free play relate in short- and long-term with children’s playfulness and whether these roles can be evaluated as facilitative or impeding. The findings revealed only small associations between teachers’ roles and children’s playfulness. This suggests that the roles that teachers adopt during children’s play have minimal effect on children’s playfulness, and other predictors such as familial and individual characteristics may be more important. Additionally, moderation

analyses indicate that the effects of these roles can vary depending on children's initial playfulness levels.

Significance of teachers' roles in supporting children's playfulness

Our results demonstrated no significant relation between teachers' roles and children's playfulness in the cross-sectional analysis. However, we found a small but significant positive longitudinal association with the onlooker role, indicating that when teachers were more frequently observed in the onlooker role at T1, children demonstrated significantly higher playfulness at T2. This suggests that teachers' preference for the onlooker role may reflect a pedagogical approach that has a gradual impact over time. In the onlooker role, teachers are present but assume a passive role in their interactions with the children, which allows a high degree of autonomy in their free play (Veiga et al., 2016). This may foster the development of children's playfulness due to increased motivation through self-determination (Frost et al., 2005; McInnes et al., 2011). Moreover, teachers in this role observe the children closely, which is considered crucial to facilitating interactions that are tailored appropriately to the children's needs (Trawick-Smith & Dziurgot, 2011).

In addition to the onlooker role, the roles of redirector and classroom manager showed marginal associations with children's playfulness in the longitudinal analysis. The small negative correlation with the classroom manager role suggests that teachers' responding frequently to children's behavior without reference to current play activities may hinder the development of playfulness. Such repeated interruptions likely prevent children from fully engaging in their play, which is essential for fostering playfulness. The classroom manager role has received little attention in international research but is commonly observed in German-speaking contexts (e.g., Kucharz et al., 2014). This raises the question whether managing and regulating children's behavior during play is culturally specific or whether it occurs more frequently due to structural characteristics, such as higher teacher-child ratios. However, the lack of reference to children's play alone does not seem to fully explain the negative association. In the redirector role as well, teachers proactively interact with children during free play without reference to children's play, yet this role was positively associated with children's playfulness at T2. This may be because teachers use this proactive support to enhance children's skills, such as language development and prosocial behavior, which in turn may support the development of playfulness. Other roles previously described as beneficial in the literature, such as co-player, tutor, and stage manager (e.g., Johnson et al., 2005), did not show significant associations with children's playfulness. Although these roles might allow teachers to positively influence children's immediate play experiences (e.g., Perren et al., 2019), they may not impact children's overall capacity to engage in play, which is reflected in the more generalized, situation-independent assessment of children's playfulness. It can also be assumed that children's playfulness overall depends more on individual-level predictors such as age, competencies, and skills and family-level predictors such as the number of siblings and the quality of the parent-child relationship (e.g., Ata & Macun, 2022; Wustmann Seiler et al., 2024).

Developmentally appropriate practice in play support

The roles of redirector and uninvolved showed different associations with children's playfulness at T2 that depend on how playful children were initially. Children who were initially less playful benefited more when teachers frequently adopted the redirector role. This suggests that when teachers focus on activities and content without reference to children's play, it can be particularly advantageous for children that struggle to engage in play. This aligns with previous research indicating that playfulness is linked to cognitive development such as executive functions (e.g., Duss et al., 2024). For children that are less playful, promoting specific skills such as language and cognitive development by engaging with children in the redirector role may lead to more playfulness over time. However, for children who were initially more playful, such interactions appeared to inhibit further development of their playfulness. The findings related to teachers' uninvolved roles support the idea that children with higher initial playfulness develop best when teachers are not directly involved in their play. For these children, autonomy seems to be a crucial factor in fostering their playfulness (e.g., Frost et al., 2005; McInnes et al., 2011). In contrast, initially less playful children may lose important learning opportunities when teachers adopt the uninvolved role. The absence of teacher support in this passive role may lead to children feeling less secure, which in turn makes it harder for them to fully engage in play. These results are in line with previous findings demonstrating that active parental play support only leads to more playfulness in children that are initially less playful (Duss et al., 2024). The roles of redirector and uninvolved represent the two extremes of teacher involvement and have previously been labeled as impeding (Johnson et al., 2005). However, the present results suggest that these roles can also be beneficial for certain children. A general classification of these roles as either facilitative or impeding in relation to children's playfulness may not always be entirely accurate. Instead, aligning the teacher's role with the specific needs of each child may be more appropriate and helpful (Trawick-Smith & Dziurgot, 2011).

Limitations

In this study, we assessed teachers' roles in free play with a five-point scale in standardized observations and for the first time examined the long-term relationship between teachers' roles and children's playfulness. Nevertheless, the study has some limitations. As 49.8% of mothers held a university degree, compared to 38% nationally (BFS, 2024), the sample represents families with relatively high socioeconomic status, which may limit the generalizability of the results. In addition, the sample size of 62 teachers was relatively small, which may account for the marginally significant findings. Future studies could examine the roles of teachers in a larger sample. This would also allow more complex analyses, for example, multi-level analyses and structural equation models. Moreover, the limited associations could reflect children's already high initial levels of playfulness, potential constraints of averaging parent and teacher ratings, or more influential factors outside the institutional setting, such as individual competencies and family factors (e.g., Ata & Macun, 2022). Alternatively, small effects might suggest that the role of adults in children's development is less influential than previously thought (Jenni, 2024). In ECEC, where one teacher is responsible for several children, peers and peer play are assumed to have a potentially greater effect on the

development of playfulness than the teacher's support. Additionally, Bronfenbrenner's (1979) ecosystem approach suggests that parents play a more important role in their children's play development than teachers do (LaForett & Mendez, 2017). Furthermore, the roles described in this study represent different types of behavior without distinguishing their qualitative aspects. This means that the quality of interactions within each role may vary, for example, in terms of teachers' sensitivity. As teacher roles were assessed only at T1, reciprocal influences between teachers' roles and children's playfulness cannot be excluded. Future studies could therefore examine teacher's roles during free play with regard to both their stability over time and their relation to children's needs in specific play situations.

Conclusion

Free play is a fundamental learning activity in early childhood education and care, which renders the facilitation of play a crucial pedagogical skill for teachers. Promoting children's playfulness is particularly important as the foundation of learning through play. Teachers assume various roles during free play, traditionally categorized as either facilitative (e.g., co-player, onlooker, tutor) or impeding (e.g., redirector, uninvolved) depending on their immediate impact on children's play (Johnson et al., 2005). However, this study did not confirm these classifications with children's playfulness, a more general, situation-independent capacity to engage in play. The onlooker role was the only one positively associated with children's playfulness at T2. This suggests that when teachers are present but take a passive role, they provide children with a sense of security while allowing them enough autonomy to engage freely in play. By closely observing, teachers can identify and respond to children's needs. Individualized support appears to be crucial, because the results show that different roles are beneficial depending on children's initial playfulness level. Children that are very playful thrive in autonomous play without proactive teacher involvement, whereas children that are less playful benefit more from proactive teacher support. Nevertheless, all associations were very small, which indicates that teachers' play involvement cannot simply be divided into facilitative or impeding to children's playfulness but that a differentiated view of teachers' roles is required in relation to children's needs.

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Data availability statement

The datasets generated for this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used chatgpt.com in order to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Appendix

Descriptive parameters of the items of the Children’s Playfulness Scale (Barnett 1991; N = 393)

Items	T1			T2		
	M	SD	r _{IT}	M	SD	r _{IT}
Manifest joy ($\alpha_{T1} = 0.79$; $\alpha_{T2} = 0.84$)						
1 The child shows emotions while playing	4.12	0.64	.51	4.09	0.78	.61
2 The child demonstrates exuberance during play	4.24	0.62	.62	4.3	0.69	.63
3 The child shows enthusiasm during play	4.27	0.57	.60	4.4	0.64	.69
4 The child sings and talks while playing	4.09	0.76	.50	4.2	0.79	.66
5 The child expresses enjoyment during play	4.61	0.45	.67	4.7	0.48	.68
Cognitive spontaneity ($\alpha_{T1} = 0.66$; $\alpha_{T2} = 0.73$)						
6 The child assumes different character roles in play	3.94	0.82	.45	4.02	0.85	.54
7 The child uses unconventional objects in play	3.74	.81	.40	3.85	0.89	.55
8 The child stays with one activity rather than changes activity during play	3.65	.75	.34	3.94	0.77	.38
9 the child invents his/her own games to play	4.14	.65	.59	4.28	0.73	.61
Social spontaneity ($\alpha_{T1} = 0.80$; $\alpha_{T2} = 0.84$)						
10 the child plays cooperatively with other children	3.75	0.70	.71	3.89	0.75	.73
11 The child responds easily to others’ approaches during play	3.78	0.66	.63	3.92	0.71	.68
12 The child is willing to share playthings	3.52	0.77	.62	3.71	0.73	.68
Sense of humor ($\alpha_{T1} = 0.81$; $\alpha_{T2} = 0.82$)						
13 The child gently teases others while at play	3.05	0.82	.56	3.25	0.91	.57
14 the child enjoys joking with other children	3.29	0.84	.71	3.64	0.89	.78
15 The child laughs at humorous stories	4.04	0.68	.67	4.30	0.72	.68
16 The child tells funny stories	3.52	0.88	.62	3.84	0.86	.67
Physical spontaneity ($\alpha_{T1} = 0.84$; $\alpha_{T2} = 0.86$)						
17 the child runs (skips, hops, jumps) a lot in play	4.05	0.77	.71	4.11	0.87	.75
18 The child prefers to be active rather than quiet in play	3.68	0.83	.67	3.79	0.90	.71
19 The child is physically active during play	4.04	0.71	.76	4.20	0.68	.78
Total score of children’s playfulness ($\alpha_{T1} = 0.67$; $\alpha_{T2} = 0.79$).						